

Author instructions: Corpus or Collection Presentation

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1 General remarks

The aim of the corpus presentations is to present an important resource in the field of Language and Aging Research (LAR).

In terms of Research Data Management, it is meant to give a proper technical description of how the data in the corpus is collected and disseminated, and provide a space where interested researchers can find an overview of existing data, the variables covered, and associated workflows, as well as considerations for ethical issues with collected data in the LAR domain. Important questions include how or to what extent (all or part of) the data are made available, whether publicly with an appropriate license, on request, or in some other manner.

The detailed description should consist of the items listed in Section 2. Depending on the specifics of your corpus some of these might not apply, but the features that make it applicable to LAR should definitely be included.

As you write your paper, please follow JLAR’s Information for Authors (JLAR editors 2023) and make sure that every internet resource and every tool is referenced with a complete entry in the bibliography.

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This is a new format for the *Journal of Language and Aging Research* and the community it serves, and so the editors are happy to receive feedback on the ways presenting a corpus feels both meaningful for a specific corpus and helpful to its readers.

2 Structure of the corpus presentation

For the corpus presentation, the editors suggest using the basic structure of a data paper. Thus, the general structure could follow the outline below. If you would like to see examples of various types of data description papers, you can most easily find them in open access data journals (AG Forschungsdaten 2024).

The corpus presentation should be a readable, concise description of the corpus with a motivation, why the data is important to Language and Aging Research and at least one example on how to use the data set. The corpus presentation should have less than 3,500 words including the references. The corpus presentation should include at least one figure, which gives some insight into either the data or the data gathering process.

Making research data FAIR—that is, findable (F), available (A), interoperable (I), and reusable (R)—has become an important standard in research data management (Wilkinson et al. 2016; GO FAIR International Support and Coordination Office (GFISCO) 2024). Authors should consider FAIR principles in their description and should explicitly state whether the data in the corpus is available for reuse and what the limitations of that might be.

If your corpus data is not yet publicly available, please consider the possibility of sharing it in public repositories such as Zenodo (European Organization for Nuclear Research and OpenAIRE 2013) or the Open Science Framework (OSF, Center for Open Science 2011–2024).

The corpus repository should include its “versioning”, with a first version 1.0 and following updates listed as new versions with the corresponding dates.

1. Background/Introduction

- (a) General description of the corpus and its motivation
- (b) Approach to Language and Aging Research (LAR)

2. Methods

- (a) Population(s) in the corpus, including age ranges
- (b) Whether the data is anonymized in the text and media files, and if so how
- (c) Language(s) covered
- (d) Data collection methods
- (e) Procedures and workflow of transcription, including software used
- (f) Quality control methods used
- (g) Explanatory materials, e.g., transcription guide

3. Corpus description

- (a) Website location

- (b) Responsible entities and copyright/license holders
- (c) Publication date and "how to cite", if possible including a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), to make it more easily citeable and findable
- (d) Size of the data, in terms of file size and number of samples
- (e) Data type (e.g., text, audio, TextGrid, . . .)
- (f) Encoding system and format used for text, sound recordings, images, graphics, video, and other data; if the format is proprietary or not widely supported—e.g., something other than UTF-8 for text—explain why the choice was made and how continued access can be guaranteed
- (g) Set of textual tags for, e.g., pauses, different languages and varieties, proper names, and of structural tags for, e.g., speaker, overlapping speech, reported speech, individual sections, anonymized sections
- (h) Transcription type (e.g., time-aligned, orthographical, phonetic, discourse analytic, . . .)
- (i) Linguistic annotation and availability of standoff annotation and code books
- (j) Indexing method(s) used, and methods available for searching the corpus
- (k) Availability of applicable scripts, e.g. for Praat (Boersma 2001), and the format used for dataframes, including whether they can be easily loaded into open source tools such as R (R Core Team 2024)
- (l) Metadata structures, including whether standards are used, e.g. of the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (1995–2024), or of the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI, Technical Council of the TEI Consortium 2021)
- (m) Availability of metadata (or data) in Zenodo (European Organization for Nuclear Research and OpenAIRE 2013), OSF (Center for Open Science 2011–2024), or similar
- (n) Supplementary material/appendix data location (e.g., stimulus material, experiment software, cleaning scripts, analysis scripts, code books), related data sets

4. Reuse Potential

- (a) Findability of the corpus in relevant inventories, and presentation in dedicated papers
- (b) Level of public accessibility for corpus data, including conditions for access (license agreement, user registration, usage restrictions) and legal constraints or copyright restrictions on access. Note: due to the nature of language data in aging research, access and reusability might be limited due to privacy laws, and this should be explicitly stated
- (c) Whether authentication is needed to download the data
- (d) Methods for accessing and reading data and metadata, including whether it be accessed by open source software and on all common operating systems
- (e) Methods for integrating data downloads into a workflow using scripting languages and tools, including the availability of source code for doing so
- (f) Steps taken to ensure that the data and metadata will remain available into the future

- (g) Whether the data and metadata can be loaded into other tools/repositories
 - (h) Ways in which the data and metadata meet community needs, and possibilities for expanding the data and metadata as community needs change
5. Ethical considerations
 - (a) Ethics committee approval, if necessary
 - (b) An ethics statement, in line with The British Association for Applied Linguistics (2021), particularly in the absence of ethics committee approval
 - (c) Informed consent
 - (d) How the protection of vulnerable populations is ensured
 6. Acknowledgements
 7. Funding
 8. Competing Interests

3 Examples and case studies

It would be good to illustrate the type of data with some examples from the corpus. Including even a short data analysis, which showcases a way to use the data. This could be one from another publication that used this corpus (or a reanalysis). You can also provide some more descriptive statistics on the data sets, which highlights the nature of the corpus.

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